

Appendix A- Countries, Year, Number of Stamps, and Description

Country	Year	Number of stamps	Description
Albania	1986, 2009	3	Transportation Workers Day, Traffic light, traffic safety
Algeria	1978, 2009, 2013, 2017	5	Children With Traffic Signs and Cars, road safety
Andorra, French	2002	1	Traffic Safety Education in Schools
Argentina	1948, 1968, 1969, 1971, 1981, 1982, 1989, 2007	13	Traffic Signs, Traffic Safety, traffic police, lights, road safety year
Aruba	2001	1	Children at Crosswalk
Australia	1975, 1990, 2022	4	Bent Wheel, Road Safety, don't drink and drive, seat belts
Austria	1971, 1975, 1997	3	Watch Out for Children, seat belt, guide dog
Bahrain	1974, 1984	5	Hand Signals and Traffic Signals, traffic week
Bangladesh	2004	1	World Health Day: Road Safety is No Accident
Barbados	1985	1	Traffic Officer, 1932
Belgium	1947, 1972, 1986, 2003, 2013	6	Railroad Crossing, traffic signs, traffic police
Bermuda	1979, 1981	2	Cycle and Police Traffic Stand, Girl Helping Blind Man Cross Street
Bolivia	1984	2	Jaywalking, Policeman
Botswana	1990	3	Children Playing on Road, accident, livestock on road
Brazil	1972, 1995, 2003, 2012	6	Pedestrians and Signal, seat belt, don't drink and drive (x2)
Bulgaria	1988, 1989, 1990	3	Vehicles; Traffic Safety, Children, Intl. Traffic Safety Year
Canada	1966	1	Traffic Signs
Central African Republic	1967, 1975, 1977	8	Traffic Light, signs (x 7)
Chile	1974, 1996	7	Traffic Police, safety awareness block drivign safety and Don't Drink and Drive (x2)
China, People's Republic of	1981, 1998	2	Pedestrian Crossing, traffic control
China, Republic of (Taiwan)	1965, 1969, 1988, 1991, 2019	7	Street Crossing, Traffic Light, Traffic Safety Year, Don't Drink and Drive
Christmas Island	1991	1	Traffic Control
Colombia	1968	1	Signal Lights
Costa Rica	1981	1	Banco Popular, Children, Traffic Policeman
Croatia	2015	1	Traffic Safety
Cuba	1970, 2012, 2014, 2016, 2019	17	Traffic Signs, road safety campaign, national traffic day (x12), children safety, motorcycle safety

Cyprus	1986	3	Road Safety: Pedestrian Crossing, helmets, seatbelts
Czech Republic/Czechoslovakia	1977, 1978, 1992	3	Children, Traffic Sign, skid marks child, traffic safety
Denmark	1970, 1977, 1990	3	Road Safety: Cycle Wheel at Crosswalk, Bike hit by car, Don't drink and drive
Ecuador	2008	1	Guayas Province Transit Commission - Traffic Policeman
Egypt	1959, 1966, 1989, 1990, 2002	5	Traffic signs, traffic safety, traffic safety conference
Estonia	2022	1	Road Safety, on Reflective Plastic Film, s/a
Fiji	1982	1	Police Car, Traffic Police
Finland	1966, 1978, 1979	3	Road Accident Victim, traffic signs, street crossing
France	1960, 1965, 1968, 2001, 2004, 2021	6	School Traffic Sign, road signs, safety, traffic laws, Don't drink and drive
Gambia	1975	3	Intl. Women's Year, Venus Symbol, Teaching, Nursing, Directing Traffic
Germany	1953, 1965, 1971, 1972, 1979, 1982, 1983, 1991, 1997	19	Prevent Traffic Accidents, signs, accident prevention, traffic safety, children, don't drink and drive (x2)
Germany Berlin	1960, 1971, 1972, 1973	6	Girl Going to School, traffic safety, don't drink and drive
Germany DDR	1966, 1969, 1970, 1975	14	Traffic Safety, signs, vehicle inspection, rail crossing, Glass of Beer, Ambulance, Motorcycle
Ghana	1974	5	Traffic Diagram at Traffic Circle, right hand driving change
Gibraltar	1980	1	Traffic Officer
Great Britain	1979	2	Police Constable directing Traffic and Children
Great Britain - Alderney	2003	2	Policeman assisting Child on Bicycle, at traffic accident
Greece	1986, 2022	7	European Road Safety, Motorcycle, traffic lights, bikes, seat belts
Guyana	1988	10	Do Not Drink and Drive (x4) safe driving animals/children
Hong Kong	2006, 2019	2	Traffic Police
Hungary	1961, 1964, 1973, 1976	8	Traffic Light, traffic safety, don't drink and drive, bike
Iceland	1968	1	Introduction of Right-hand Driving in Iceland
India	1991	1	Traffic Safety
Indonesia	2001	1	National Police With Children and Helicopter, Zebra Crossing Sign
Iraq	1971, 1972, 1989	7	Traffic Safety, Children, police day

Israel	1966, 1982, 1993, 1997	13	Road Sign and Motorcyclist, child, traffic safety, Don't Drink and Drive
Italy	1932, 1957, 1984, 2004, 2008	7	Road Direction Sign, traffic safety, road sfaety, traffic police
Japan	1967, 1969	2	Traffic Safety, Automobile, Children
Jordan	1977, 1985	5	Traffic Safety, Motorcycle Policeman
Kenya	1978	6	Traffic Safety
Kiribati	2004	4	Traffic Safety, Automobile, Children
Korea, DPR	1987	4	Traffic Signs
Korea, South	1990	1	Traffic Safety, Teddy Bear in Hospital
Kuwait	1966, 1967, 1968, 1969, 1970	11	Traffic Signal,police, traffic day
Kyrgyzstan	1995	1	Traffic Safety, Stylized Butterfly
Latvia	1995	1	European Safe Driving Week
Lebanon	1995, 2018	2	Road Users respect this Cane, traffic safety
Libya	1974, 1979	4	Traffic Signs: Automobile and Touring Club of Libya, child drawing police
Luxembourg	1970, 1979, 1980, 1986, 2010	5	Traffic Safety, Child, signs
Macao	2016	1	Police Officer on Traffic Duty
Malta	1984	1	Traffic Duty
Mexico	1991, 1993, 2004, 2009, 2011	5	Prevent Transportation Accidents, traffic safety, lights
Mongolia	1971, 1998	3	Traffic Lights, road signs
Morocco	1972, 1980, 2006	4	Yellow Road Marking, traffic signs, traffic safety
Namibia	2011	1	Road Safety Campaign
Netherlands	1959, 1974, 1980, 1985, 1994	9	Children Crossing Street in Crosswalk, bike, road signs, traffic safety
Netherlands Antilles	1973, 1993, 1995, 2002	6	Traffic Safety: Pedestrian Crossing, Traffic Sign, childrenlights, seat belts
Netherlands New Guinea	1962	2	Need for Road Safety, School Children Crossing Street, traffic signs
New Caledonia	1977, 1980, 2010	4	Traffic Safety
New Zealand	1964, 1985, 1995, 1996, 2008	11	National Road Safety Campaign, children, bike, seat belts (x3)
Niger	1979, 1986	3	Traffic Safety
Nigeria	1972, 2008	3	Introduction of Right-hand Driving in Nigeria, Car, Bicycle, Motorcycle, Federal Road Safety Commission

Oman	1981, 1998, 2010, 2013	5	Policewoman and Children Crossing Street, Traffic Week, Traffic Safety Day
Palestinian Authority	2012, 2013	2	Traffic Road Sign, Police directing traffic
Papua New Guinea	1962	1	Traffic Police
Paraguay	2010	1	Road Safety Day
Peru	2008	1	Traffic Policeman
Poland	1948, 1969, 2020	5	Traffic Safety, Railroad crossing gates
Portugal	1972, 1978, 1979, 1982, 1991,1994, 2001, 2020	14	Road Marking, Don't drink and drive (x2), traffic safety, year of road safety
Qatar	1967, 1969, 1975, 1978, 1985	12	Traffic Light and Intersection, traffic police, traffic safety
Romania	1975, 1982, 1987	8	Publicity for Traffic Rules, Traffic safety, bike
Russia	1972, 1979, 1990, 1996, 2000, 2004, 2009, 2013, 2016, 2020	17	Traffic Safety Campaign, Child Reading Traffic Rules
Saint Helena	1981	1	Traffic Guards Taking Oath
Salvador, El	1990	1	Road Signs, Automobiles
Saudi Arabia	1969, 1999	4	Traffic Safety, traffic signals
Sierra Leone	1971, 1981	3	Traffic Pattern Shaped Stamp, traffic safety
Singapore	1988, 2003	2	Road Safety, Courtesy Campaign, traffic police
Slovenia	2022, 2023	2	Campaign Promoting Use of Seat Belts, pedestrian safety
Somalia	1963	1	Traffic Police
South Africa	2004	1	Road Safety
Spain	1976, 1993, 2005, 2009, 2011, 2012, 2013	11	Traffic Safety, road safety, seat belt, civic values children
Surinam	2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004	17	Traffic Signs
Swaziland	2005	4	Traffic Safety, Car, Firefighters at Accident Scene
Sweden	1967, 1971, 2000	7	Right Hand Driving as Seen Though Windshield, traffic safety, children
Switzerland	1956, 1969, 1980	3	Children Crossing Street and Road Signs, Traffic Safety, traffic lights
Syria	1966, 1971, 1982, 1986	6	Traffic Safety Day, Stop Light, children, world traffic day
Tanzania	1978	5	Traffic Safety, children, don't drink and drive (x2)

Thailand	1988	1	Traffic Safety
Tonga	1991, 1992, 2004	8	Don't Drink and Drive (x3)
Tunisia	1973, 1975, 1979, 1995, 2013	6	Traffic Safety, children, accident prevention
Turkey	1977, 1981, 1987, 1988, 1990	14	Traffic Safety, don't drink and drive (x3)
Turkish Rep. of No. Cyprus	1990, 2013, 2015	7	Traffic Safety, road safety, seat belt, civic values children
Turks and Caicos Islands	1983	1	Woman Crossing Guard, Children
Uganda	1990	3	Looking Before Crossing Street, seat belts, bike children
Ukraine	2005	1	Safety - Green Light, Children
United Arab Emirates	1973	12	Traffic Safety, children,
United Nations - Geneva	2004	2	Road Map and Road Safety
United Nations - New York	2004	2	Automobile, Traffic Safety
United Nations - Vienna	2004	2	Road Map and Road Safety
United States	1952, 1965	2	Traffic Safety, Children, traffic signal
Uruguay	1990, 2012	8	Traffic Safety, Car, Bus, Don't Drink and Drive
Viet Nam, Socialist Republic	2011, 2020, 2021, 2022	14	Decade for Road Safety, don't drink and drive (x2), traffic safety strategies
Wallis and Futuna Islands	2019	1	Road Safety Campaign
Yemen Arab Republic	1966	3	Traffic Day
Yemen, PDR	1977	1	Traffic Policeman, Traffic Changeover to Right Hand Side of Road
Zimbabwe	2012	4	Traffic Safety